

EMOTIONS, THOUGHTS AND SUGGESTIONS OF GRADUATE STUDENTS ON SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH METHODS AND PUBLICATION ETHICS COURSE

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What are the reasons for participating in the joint Scientific Research Methods and Publication Ethics course of the students enrolled in the Graduate School of Educational Sciences, the benefits it provides, the quality of the education provided and the views on the additional course? In this study, the phenomenological method of qualitative research was used. Since the research is qualitative, no universe and sample determination were made. The appropriate working group was used. Students claimed that they attended this program because of “academic career, specialization and self-development”. It can be said that, the criticism and suggestions of the students toward the course are collected in the dimension of "system, course, lecturer, suggestions and affective". It can be argued that their views on the additional course are in the categories of "productive, unproductive and I could not participate". Students want to consider student requests and conditions, reduce the number of students, use the system effectively with the least number of error, extend the course duration, and give feedback and corrections to each student while doing distance education.

Keywords: Scientific Research, University, Student, Emotion, Thought, Suggestion

Introduction

Each cultivation can be evaluated before, during and after application. Adult evaluation models can be used during the evaluation process. These models may differ (Sönmez & Alacapınar, 2015; Uşun, 2012). Whichever model you use, there may be stakeholders to consult about the adult. These stakeholders can be students, teachers, administrators, supervisors, servants, parents, other people and systems that affect and are affected by the inputs, operations, and outputs of the system. The most important of these stakeholders are students; because they are the basic element of the educational system. Without the student, no educational system can exist and be prepared. In this context, students' opinions on the education system can be curicial .

In this process, it can be determined which gains (target behavior) the students gained, which ones they did not gain, which ones they learned half-way. Relevant content, tutorials, and test cases can be retained. Gains, content, training and testing situations related to deficiencies, mistakes and sloppy learning can be reconsidered and corrected according to students' views. Thus, the catch can be made more consistent.

In the process of preparing, applying, evaluating and developing a talent, seeking student opinions is a principle of talent development. Every education trainee is prepared for the student and put to work. In this context, one of the determining elements of scientific achievements (target behaviors) is the individual, that is, the student (Ertürk, 1972; Sönmez, 2012). The student's intelligence, special and general ability, knowledge, skill, level of perception and intuition, socio-economic, political, psychological, that is, cultural structure can affect what, how, why, when and why he/she will learn. These can affect and determine both the achievements, content, and the training and testing situations.

Problem Statement

What are the reasons for participating in the joint Scientific Research Methods and Publication Ethics course of the students enrolled in the Graduate School of Educational Sciences, the benefits it provides, the quality of the education provided and the views on the additional course?

Sub Problems

1- What are the opinions of graduate students of the Graduate School of Educational Sciences regarding the reasons for continuing their graduate education and the contribution of the program to them?

2- What are the opinions of the graduate students of the Graduate School of Educational Sciences regarding the criticism and suggestions for the course?

3- What are the opinions of the graduate students of the Institute of Educational Sciences regarding the additional course outside the classroom?

Methodology

The phenomenological approach of qualitative research was used in the research. In qualitative research, different types of interviews can be used as focus group interviews, observation, archive and document data collection methods (Creswell, 2013).

Working group

The study was conducted with 140 students who took the joint Scientific Research and Publication Ethics course in a university's education faculty graduate program in the 2020 -2021 academic year.

Data Collection and Analysis

Reasons for continuing postgraduate education about the course for graduate students, the contribution of the program to them; their criticisms and suggestions for the course, their feelings and thoughts about the extra course outside the course were collected at the end of the term by using Google forms, one of the web 2.0 tools. Ensuring validity and reliability in qualitative research can be achieved with credibility, transferability, consistency and confirmability (Sönmez & Alacapınar, 2014; Güçlü, 2019).

Findings

In this section, data related to sub-problems were collected and the data collected with Google forms were examined, tables created using percentages and frequencies were explained and interpreted.

Findings Related to the First Sub-problem

The reasons for continuing postgraduate education of the Graduate School of Educational Sciences students and their views on the contribution of the program are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Categories of Students' Reasons and Opinions on Contribution

Categories	frequency	percentage
Academic career, specialization	55	21,24
Self- development	125	48,26
Being a qualified teacher professional development	34	13,13
Scientific thinking article writing	34	13,13
Self- regulation self- respect	11	4,25

Total

259

100

As shown in Table 1, the categories of students' reasons for continuing their graduate education and their contributions are academic career, specialization, self-development, professional development, scientific thinking, article writing, self-regulation-self-esteem. According to these data, it can be said that students generally gather in the categories of "academic career, specialization and self-development". The written statements requested from volunteer students regarding these categories are summarized and presented below:

Participant 1: I started my master's degree due to my academic career planning. With my master's degree, I aim to complete my doctorate without wasting time. While choosing my undergraduate program, my first target was the academy. I do not see myself as a teacher in the Ministry of National Education (MEB) in the future, but as a faculty member at the university. To improve myself, to have different perspectives, to be aware of the updated literature and most importantly to be happy. Researching and academic life makes me happy. The achievement that I think will add to me is the ability to follow studies.

Participant 2: I have with precious professors that I take as an example in the field. I want to be a successful university teacher like them one day. In fact, I would like to put forward a new theory and be remembered and thought in the future like many valuable scientists whose names we are now commemorating. I thought that my inquiring and investigative side would be nourished by postgraduate education. In this course, I learned how to conduct scientific research. It was instructive as I had the opportunity to apply what I learned. I think that the implementations made a positive contribution. I learned to review articles. I can say that it is useful because I learned to write a thesis proposal. Being able to do scientific research and write a thesis, in short, is a crucial course that must be taken to be a researcher.

Participant 3: I think that all humanity has one purpose while living life. Regardless of whether it is good or bad, we are all concerned about leaving a mark on the blank canvas called life. When the canvases of all of us are put on top of each other, the concept called life emerges. As much as I could, I wanted the traces I left to be more permanent and beneficial to humanity, albeit a point. In short, I have embarked on this path both to learn and to prove to myself that I exist in life.

Participant 4: I think that these trainings I have received will improve my vision. I want to be appointed as a teacher with a master's degree. I think that the program will greatly contribute to my knowledge and experience. I want to apply all that I have learned. I want to read more and improve. Above all, I hope to broaden my perspective on life and to be able to look at the world and universe from a wider perspective, and to advance my self-regulation and self-respect.

Participant 5: A program that gives me an opportunity to improve myself. Simultaneously, I think it will be beneficial for me to advance in my profession

in the future. It allows me to look at education from a different perspective. We can see the deficiencies in our country and produce solutions about them. First, , I wanted it for my personal development. My goal is not only to settle in an academic staff, but in today's digital age, learning occurs by ourselves, so every person must learn to conduct research. I wanted to be more productive for my students in the institution I will be appointed by learning how to conduct research in an ethical way.

Findings Related to the Second Sub-problem

The criticism and suggestions of the graduate students of the Graduate School of Educational Sciences are categorized and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Categories of Students' Opinions on Criticism and Suggestions for the Course

Categories	frequency	percentage
System oriented	69	24,47
For the lesson	133	47,16
For lecturer	30	10,64
Suggestions	39	13,83
For the affective dimension	11	3,90
Total	282	100

As it can be seen in Table 2, it can be said that the categories of the students' criticisms and suggestions about the course are collected in the dimension of "from the system, toward the course, toward the lecturer, suggestions and affective". It can be said that students state their criticisms and suggestions about the "system and course". Written statements requested from volunteer students regarding these categories are summarized and presented below:

Participant 1: It was a lesson that was not easy to understand. In addition to the fact that the course is a difficult course in normal processes, I think it becomes more difficult with distance education. During the course, I encountered many issues that I had difficulty in understanding. In this course, which I think can be beneficial for me, I think that I could not get enough efficiency due to the distance education system. Thanks to the course supported by the book, the quality of the education I received increased a little, but the constant corrections of wrong examples caused confusion for me. Systemic problems also caused negativities in the understanding of the lesson.

Participant 2: First, I want to thank you for your efforts by checking the work of so many students and giving feedback. Many courses have been in distance education up to a point, but I can say that it was difficult for

this course to be distance education with so many students due to the importance of this course, in terms of efficiency. I think we could not have benefited so much if not for your efforts and individual transfer. I can say that the rapid progress in the first weeks had a negative effect on motivation. I think this situation occurred because of the trainings that will occur in the following weeks. Thank you for your hard work, teacher.

Participant 3. Distance education was a bit of a problem. Since there are too many students taking the course, our teacher's ability to take care of himself has decreased. I could not obtain satisfactory information about the processes of the courses. It was a problem in terms of communication that we were teaching the courses not on the university's own system but on other systems. Despite all these problems, our teacher's self-sacrificing behavior was admirable. Only system problems prevented us from understanding the lesson very well. But under these conditions, it could have been that much. There could also be a separate course for doctoral students.

Participant 4. From my viewpoint, I find the lesson productive under the conditions of the pandemic. Of course, it would be better to take this training face-to-face and be in one-on-one communication with my teachers and friends; but we are going through a difficult time and I think it was the best that could happen under these circumstances. Although the course and subjects are heavy, I believe that we reinforce it thanks to the homework we do regularly. In addition, since I followed the lessons regularly every week, the efficiency I got was high. The main course that an academic should know throughout his life is the course of scientific research methods. This course is also offered at the undergraduate level. However, a more detailed and detailed explanation at the graduate level made it easier for us to practice. In short, I was satisfied with this course. Thank you to our dear teachers.

Participant 5. Being taking this course with 200 people at the same time during the term affected the process badly. I think that I cannot achieve effective learning and I have difficulties in homework. Despite all efforts of our teacher, getting feedback was low. I think that this process is not easy for both the students and our teacher. I would prefer to take my course with my own department.

Participant 6: My dear teacher patiently examined our homeworks one by one each week. He knew our mistakes were his own fault in the beginning; What an elegant and beautiful idea. It would be unfair not to attend the lecture of such a gracious teacher carefully and to make mistakes. I listened to each additional lesson with my breath held, and I enjoyed it immensely and learned a lot. Infinitely thank you.

Findings Related to the Third Sub-problem

The opinions of the graduate students of the Graduate School of Educational Sciences regarding the additional course outside the classroom are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Students' Opinions on the Additional Course

Categories	frequency	percentage
Efficient (Useful)	109	75,69
Inefficient	24	16,67
I couldn't join the system	11	7,64
Total	144	100

As shown in Table 3, it can be said that the students' views on the additional course are grouped under the categories of "productive, unproductive and I could not participate". It can be said that students' opinions are gathered in the "useful (efficient) category. The written statements requested from the students regarding these categories are summarized and presented below:

Participant 1: Our teacher voluntarily arranged the additional lessons for us to improve, so we can't thank him enough. It is done because of your sacrifices. I am aware that this situation is due to your efforts to enlighten us. You set an example for us with your determination. Scientific research methods are a difficult course and learning it online is even more difficult, but thanks to additional lessons and supplements, we have been productive. With the repetitions of the lessons, it becomes easier to fit what is told. Thanks to you, I have gained a new perspective. Thank you. Showing the examples we made in the supplementary lesson helped us to reinforce. I saw that I could also look at things from the perspective of different disciplines. When my own homework came across, I realized my mistakes. When I saw the ones of my other friends, I transferred them to my own and furthered the process. I think we learned by doing.

Participant 2: Your additional study shows your dedication and how much you want to eliminate the problems arising from this system. We, as students, have truly honored that you have left the choice of day and time to us and your efforts to close our gaps as time allows. However, as long as the system does not change, I think that no matter how much additional course is given, it will not be as effective as a department-based course. Having additional lessons provided a better understanding of the examples and subject In this sense, the instructor of the course put a lot of effort and did his best to convey the subject well. Additional lessons were

*useful in this sense. But later I didn't want to participate because similar mistakes are still being made **and I am tired of listening.***

*Participant 3: Although the **additional lessons** were selfless in terms of the teacher, **they did not reach their goal.** Lessons were conducted on the analysis of several student assignments. This situation caused confusion for students whose content study was different. In this course, which was held with many students, **it could not be productive because it was impossible to correct the homework of every student. Since the additional lesson periods are long, distraction has occurred.** In this context, **I think that additional courses contribute;** however the fact that we could not communicate with our teacher one-on-one because it was a course taken with many people created inefficiency in terms of our learning.*

*Participant 4: **I do not find it appropriate to add additional lessons without asking us. Because the only job of many people like me is not only school, and I couldn't enter because it coincided with my working hours when the additional course was added. I also think that absenteeism should not be taken in additional courses; Because it is an "additional course", only those who want to attend should attend and there should be no obligation to attend.*** Again, it was unproductive because **there was too much participation and there was difficulty in reaching the teachers.**

Discussion and Conclusion

A person can have at least one goal in life. He may engage in various activities to achieve this goal. Education is one of these activities. Self-realization and development of skills can be through education. According to Maslow's triangle, every person tries fulfilling the basic physiological and gradually built needs of trust, belonging, self-respect and self-actualization at the highest level (Sönmez, Alacapınar, Zeybek, & Yıldızlı, 2019).

In this context, the students participating in the program gave answers in the categories of "academic career, specialization, self-development, professional development, scientific thinking, article writing, self-regulation-self-respect". Notice that all of these categories are related to the highest level of self-actualization in Maslow's triangle. This is a natural state. When the person reaches this level, he or she can feel happier, more comfortable and safe. The concept of life can change. Self-confidence may increase. He can also be a much sought-after person who is respected and loved by others and society. These features are related to the affective domain. The affective field can include what makes people humanize and live more consistently. There are such situations that the individual may give up on physiological needs, even living, because of what is related to the affective field (Sönmez, Alacapınar, Zeybek, & Yıldız, 2019).

Being a university lecturer in society can provide the necessary material and moral opportunities to live comfortably. When university students cannot find a job after graduation, they hope to find a job by completing a masters and

doctorate. Therefore, they can enroll in masters and doctoral programs. As a matter of fact, the students supported this judgment by saying that “I can find a job and live more comfortably when I finish this program”.

It can be said that the categories of the students' criticisms and suggestions about the course are collected in the dimension of "from the system, toward the course, toward the lecturer, suggestions and affective". It can be argued that students' criticisms and suggestions are generally related to the "system and course". The questions arising from the system were determined as the number of students being too high. Too many students can reduce the efficiency of education (Sönmez, 1987). As in the course, doing online education with a group of more than 200 can bring many problems. Many advantages of face-to-face education may disappear. It may not be possible to provide feedback, corrections, hints, reinforcements, and active participation of each student. Students expressed this situation as “I did not get enough feedback. Most of the time the same samples were corrected. I am tired of so many assignments. I could learn because of your sacrifice. It's not your fault. It is due to the system. When I have more than 200 students, which one of them can you give feedback or corrections to?” they stated. They suggested that the course be given by a faculty member who knows both the field and scientific research, or that it be divided into classes according to the field. They asked that the duration of the course be insufficient and extended. These variables can increase the efficiency of the course (Alacapınar, 2018; Bloom, 1976; Sönmez, 2012;).

Scientific research is a necessary and crucial course to become a scientist. This course should be given in all schools; because a person can solve the problems he encounters in life by using the scientific method. The students who took the course said that “it was perhaps the most important lesson of our academic life; but giving it online was inefficient because the group was crowded and mixed.” They supported this view. Most students said, “It was nice and productive. I learned a lot. I was happy to take the course for the second time. The course is interesting under normal circumstances. Mendeley and Web of Science trainings were pretty good. I will use the information I learned while writing my thesis. I think we received very, useful training . It was productive to learn many applications that even our consultants have not heard of and to have the opportunity to follow current studies in the field.

I learned many new databases, sites, opportunities that I would normally not even know about. I got a lot of additional information that will be useful to me in the future. Apart from that, it was productive to progress with your book. There was an opportunity to open and read where I hung out.” expressed their thoughts and feelings. The fact that the acquired knowledge and skills are useful to the student, learning new knowledge and skills can lead to learning and developing positive feelings toward the lesson. These positive emotions can increase success and motivation (Sönmez, 2012; Akgün & Güntaş, 2018; Duman et al., 2011). The person want to learn the knowledge and skills that will be useful to him much more. Indeed, “Especially

SPSS and NVIVO etc. I want to learn to use programs for free. It will be beneficial for everyone, especially if SPSS training is provided.” He states this view. Learning willingly, learning the knowledge and skills needed is a stimulant that increase the quality of education. If the individual knows what he/she learns will be useful in life, his/her motivation to learn can increase (Gagne & Briggs, 1979; Sönmez, 1987).

One of the most important variables affecting success is time. It is claimed that if everyone is given the time they need, they can learn anything (Carol, 1963; Bloom, 1974; Bloom, 1976). However, time alone may not be enough in education. The amount of time used can affect the results. Time can be an important variable if the teacher effectively uses the variables required by pedagogy during the learning process. In other words, if the teacher uses feedback, corrections, hints, reinforcements in the educational environment, actively involve the student in the lesson, and becomes a role model, the time spent in education can be effective. Students expressed a positive opinion about the additional course. “Especially, although there was no face-to-face training, **it was really valuable for our teacher to give immediate feedback to the questions and give additional lessons.**

An additional course application is made thanks to your sacrifices. I am aware that this situation is due to your efforts to enlighten us. You set an example for us with your determination. You worked hard for us and tried to convey the best, I am grateful to you in this regard, **The additional course was much more useful for me to adapt to this course.** He went into detail and provided a better understanding. It was useful to deal with the topics that were left in the air in a short time in the normal lesson. **Seeing examples were helpful for our study.** It helped me understand the lesson better. **Additional course time may be extended.** Lesson time was limited and he could theoretically stay in the air. It increased the efficiency in terms of intensifying the questions in our minds in the additional lessons and explaining the subject with examples. Students who expressed their feelings and thoughts by saying, **“You read the answers and give feedback from all of us without getting tired of it”, claimed that they found the additional course useful.** Very few students stated that they did not find the additional course useful.

These are “I didn't get any feedback. I couldn't attend because it was a certain time. Everyone's homework was examined one by one and feedback was not given. I am tired of working on the same and similar samples. **This course is impossible with online education. Additional lessons take time. Often times the connection drops. I must constantly renew it. So it is inefficient at all.**” They are the thoughts and feelings they express. This support what was said above about teacher and time.

Suggestions

Based on these data, some suggestions can be made.

1. Students can be classified in their own fields and take this course from a faculty member who knows both the research and field
2. The number of students can be reduced.
3. Each student should be supervised by the lecturer and his/her active participation can be ensured by providing feedback, corrections, hints and reinforcements.
4. The duration of the course can be extended.
5. The course can be opened at different times during the week.
6. The needs of the students in this regard can be determined and the course topics can be enriched.

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